

Effectiveness and Safety of Digital Health Interventions in Reducing Health Inequities in Type 2 Diabetes Management: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Effectiveness and Safety of Digital Health Interventions in Reducing Health Inequities in Type 2 Diabetes Management: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Condition or domain being studied

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus; Diabetes Mellitus; Digital health intervention; Health equity

Adults with Type 2 Diabetes receiving digital health interventions to improve clinical outcomes and reduce health inequities, compared with standard care or non-digital interventions.

Rationale for the review

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus is a prevalent chronic disease with significant health burden. Digital health interventions can improve diabetes management, but access and effectiveness may vary across populations, creating potential health inequities. This review will synthesize evidence on the effectiveness, safety, and equity impacts of digital interventions, providing guidance for practice and policy.

Review objectives

Primary Objective:

- To evaluate the effectiveness and safety of digital health interventions in improving clinical outcomes among adults with Type 2 Diabetes.

Secondary Objectives:

- To assess the impact of digital interventions on adherence, self-efficacy, quality of life, and health service utilization.
- To examine whether digital health interventions reduce or exacerbate health inequities across socioeconomic, racial/ethnic, or geographic subgroups.

Keywords

Type 2 diabetes mellitus; Chronic disease management; Digital health interventions; Health inequities; Safety and adverse events

Country

India

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Included

Adults aged 18 years and older diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus of any gender, race, ethnicity, or geographic location. All socioeconomic groups will be considered, including underserved or vulnerable populations, to assess health equity impacts.

Excluded

Individuals with Type 1 Diabetes, gestational diabetes, pre-diabetes, or other non-Type 2 diabetes conditions.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Included

Digital health intervention; mHealth; Telemedicine ; Remote digital monitoring

Digital health interventions aimed at supporting Type 2 Diabetes management, including:

- Mobile health applications (mHealth apps)
- Telemedicine or telehealth services
- SMS/text message–based interventions
- Web-based self-management platforms
- Wearable health devices and remote monitoring tools
- AI-assisted or automated digital support tools

Intervention taxonomy: digital interventions will be coded into discrete categories (mHealth/app, SMS, telemedicine/video visit, web-based platform, wearables/remote monitoring, AI-assisted). Meta-analyses will be run within homogeneous categories where ≥ 3 comparable studies exist.

Interventions delivered alone or alongside standard care.

Excluded

- Interventions that are purely educational without digital delivery (e.g., paper-based programs, in-person education only)
- Pharmacological or surgical interventions without a digital component

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Included

PICO tags selected: Usual Care; Placebo

- Standard care or usual care for Type 2 Diabetes management
- Non-digital interventions (e.g., in-person education, lifestyle counseling without digital tools)
- Placebo or sham digital interventions, if reported

Excluded

- Studies without any comparator or control group, unless they provide relevant equity or safety data for narrative synthesis

Study design

Both randomized and nonrandomized study types will be included.

Included

- Randomised controlled trials (RCTs): Parallel, cluster, or crossover designs evaluating digital health interventions for Type 2 Diabetes.
- Non-randomized studies (NRS): quasi-experimental, cohort, or controlled before–after studies assessing the same interventions.

Non-RCTs will be used primarily for safety and health equity analyses and, where appropriate, for sensitivity or supplementary meta-analyses.

Excluded

- Qualitative-only studies (e.g., interviews, focus groups)
- Reviews, protocols, case reports, or commentaries without primary outcome data

Context

- This review will include studies conducted in any healthcare setting, including primary care clinics, outpatient facilities, community health programs, or via telemedicine/digital platforms.
- There are no geographic restrictions; studies from high, middle, and low-income countries will be included.
- Both urban and rural populations will be considered to capture potential differences in access and health equity.
- Studies must report on adults (≥ 18 years) with Type 2 Diabetes and evaluate digital health interventions as defined in the inclusion criteria.

For studies reporting multiple follow-up durations, data closest to 6 months will be used for the primary analysis, with additional subgroup analyses by short, medium, and long-term time frames.

Equity dimensions will be captured through PROGRESS-Plus variables and contextual proxies (e.g., country income classification, rural/urban setting, digital access indices) to ensure representation of diverse populations (see protocol) and report equity findings narratively if quantitative pooling is not possible.

Equity outcomes will be extracted following a pre-specified hierarchy of evidence, prioritizing individual-level subgroup analyses where available, followed by reported subgroup differences, study-level contextual proxies, and finally area-level indices (e.g., country income classification, digital access indices). This hierarchical approach will enable consistent synthesis despite variable reporting of equity data.

SIMILAR REVIEWS

Check for similar records already in PROSPERO

PROSPERO identified a number of existing PROSPERO records that were similar to this one (last check made on 9 October 2025). These are shown below along with the reasons given by that the review team for the reviews being different and/or proceeding.

- Doctor-led digital health interventions to improve adherence in type 2 diabetes in primary care: a systematic review and evidence synthesis. [published 15 September 2025] [CRD420251147541]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Comparing Digital Monitoring and Educational Interventions to Standard Care for Improving Knowledge, Behaviors, and Self-Management Skills in Patients with Diabetic Foot Conditions. [published 14 April 2025] [CRD420251031856]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Effectiveness of Digital Health Interventions on Glycemic Control Among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes in Arab Countries: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 12 March 2025] [CRD420251009110]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

This record has not been submitted.

Review timeline

Start date: 1 September 2025. End date: 31 December 2025.

Date of registration in PROSPERO

This record has not been published.

AVAILABILITY OF FULL PROTOCOL

Availability of full protocol

A full protocol has not been written.

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Search for unpublished studies

Both published and unpublished studies will be sought.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched

The main databases to be searched are *CENTRAL - Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials*, *CINAHL - Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature*, *Embase - Embase via Ovid*, *MEDLINE*, *PubMed* and *Scopus*.

Search language restrictions

There are no language restrictions.

Search date restrictions

There are no search date restrictions.

Other methods of identifying studies

Other studies will be identified by: *contacting authors or experts, looking through all the articles that cite the papers included in the review ("snowballing" or forward citation searching), reference list checking (backward citation searching), searching conference proceedings and searching trial or study registers.*

Additional information about identifying studies

Additional studies will be identified by contacting authors and experts, checking reference lists of included studies, searching relevant conference proceedings, examining trial and study registers, and forward citation searching of key papers.

Link to search strategy

A full search strategy is available in the full protocol as described in the *Availability of full protocol* section

Selection process

Studies will be screened independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Other relevant information about searching and screening

Screening will be managed using systematic review software to track decisions and ensure consistency. A pilot screening of a subset of studies will be conducted to calibrate reviewers and refine eligibility criteria before full screening.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction from published articles and reports

Data will be extracted independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Authors will be asked to provide any required data not available in published reports.

Study risk of bias or quality assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using: *Cochrane RoB-2* and *ROBINS-I*

Data will be assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Additional information will be sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports.

Reporting bias assessment

For outcomes included in meta-analyses, reporting bias will be assessed using funnel plots and Egger's regression test when ≥ 10 studies are available. Protocols and trial registrations will be compared with published reports to identify selective outcome reporting. Narrative synthesis will highlight potential biases where quantitative assessment is not possible.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of evidence for each primary and secondary outcome will be evaluated using the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation) approach. This includes assessment of risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. Summary of Findings tables will be prepared to present the strength of evidence for key outcomes.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

1. Glycemic control

- Definition / Measurement: HbA1c, fasting blood glucose, time in range
- HbA1c (%) will be the primary glycemic control measure. Fasting blood glucose and time in range will be treated as secondary glycemic indicators and converted to standardized mean differences where necessary.
- Time points: Short-term (≤ 6 months), medium-term (6–12 months), long-term (> 12 months)
- Effect measure: Mean difference or standardized mean difference with 95% confidence intervals

2. Health equity outcomes

- Definition / Measurement: Differences in clinical or self-management outcomes across socioeconomic status, race/ethnicity, geographic location, or other PROGRESS-Plus factors
- Time points: As reported in included studies
- Effect measure: Relative risk, odds ratio, or mean difference, as appropriate

3. Safety

Safety outcomes include adverse clinical events, device-related failures, data-privacy breaches, or other intervention-related harms

- Definition / Measurement: Adverse events, technical failures, data breaches
- Time points: As reported
- Effect measure: Risk ratio or incidence proportion

Additional outcomes

Patient adherence / engagement

- Definition / Measurement: Medication adherence, frequency of self-monitoring, engagement with digital intervention (app usage, log-ins, module completion)
- Time points: As reported in included studies
- Effect measure: Mean difference, odds ratio, or risk ratio, as appropriate

Self-efficacy / self-management skills

- Definition / Measurement: Validated scales assessing diabetes self-efficacy, confidence, or ability to manage condition
- Time points: As reported
- Effect measure: Mean difference or standardized mean difference with 95% confidence intervals

Quality of life / patient-reported outcomes

- Definition / Measurement: Generic or diabetes-specific quality of life questionnaires (e.g., SF-36, EQ-5D, ADDQoL)

- Time points: Short-, medium-, or long-term as reported
- Effect measure: Mean difference or standardized mean difference

Health service utilization

- Definition / Measurement: Hospital admissions, emergency visits, outpatient visits, telemedicine contacts
- Time points: As reported
- Effect measure: Rate ratios, risk ratios, or mean differences

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

- Quantitative outcomes from randomized and non-randomized studies will be pooled using a random-effects meta-analysis (DerSimonian–Laird method, REML or Hartung–Knapp adjustments) where appropriate.
- DerSimonian–Laird will be used as the default random-effects estimator; REML or Hartung–Knapp adjustments will be applied in sensitivity analyses or where small-study effects are likely.
- Separate meta-analyses will be conducted for RCTs and non-RCTs. When appropriate, results from both designs will be compared narratively or combined in sensitivity analyses after examining methodological compatibility and heterogeneity.
- Continuous outcomes (e.g., HbA1c, quality of life scores) will be combined using mean differences or standardized mean differences with 95% confidence intervals.
- Dichotomous outcomes (e.g., adverse events, adherence) will be combined using risk ratios or odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals.
- Heterogeneity will be assessed using I^2 and τ^2 statistics.
- Meta-analysis will proceed where conceptual and statistical heterogeneity are acceptable ($I^2 < 75\%$); otherwise, results will be synthesized narratively.
- Where meta-analysis is not possible, results will be synthesized narratively with structured tables and figures.
- Where ≥ 10 studies are available, meta-regression may be performed to explore sources of heterogeneity (e.g., intervention type, baseline HbA1c, country income level, and follow-up duration).
- The certainty of evidence for each pooled outcome will later be assessed using the GRADE approach.
- Subgroup analyses will be conducted by intervention type, population characteristics (e.g., socioeconomic status, geographic location), and study quality.
- Cluster RCTs will be handled by adjusting the study's ICC or an assumed ICC with sensitivity analysis.
- Equity will be extracted using the PROGRESS-Plus framework including age, sex/gender, race/ethnicity, education level, occupation, income or SES quintile, health insurance status, language, disability, baseline digital literacy.

The following Equity proxies may be used:

- Country income classification (World Bank: HIC/MIC/LIC).
- Study setting: community health clinic in deprived area vs tertiary center.
- Internet/phone penetration at study's region at year of trial.
- Authors' statement that the sample was "underserved" or "low-income" or recruited from safety-net clinics.
- Rural vs urban recruitment site.

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work	✓	✓
Formal searching/study identification	✓	

Review stage**Started****Completed**

Screening search results against inclusion criteria

Data extraction or receipt of IPD

Risk of bias/quality assessment

Data synthesis

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

Publication of review results

Results of the review will be published in English.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members**Mr Aayan Dey** (review guarantor and contact) ORCID: 0009-0001-2583-5456. SSSMCRI. India.

No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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N/A

Funding source

Review has no funding and no agreed support from an academic institution and is done in authors' own time.

Peer review

There has been no peer review of this planned review.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This review will follow PRISMA 2020 and PRISMA-P 2025 guidelines for reporting, and will incorporate the PRISMA-E extension to ensure transparent reporting of health equity considerations. Emphasis will be placed on evaluating health equity outcomes using the PROGRESS-Plus framework, which is not commonly addressed in previous reviews of digital health interventions for Type 2 Diabetes. The review aims to provide actionable insights for clinicians, policymakers, and developers of digital health technologies globally.

Patient and Public Involvement (PPI):

No patients or members of the public were directly involved in the design or conduct of this review. However, the research question was informed by observed disparities in digital health access and outcomes among patients with Type 2 Diabetes. Following completion, results will be disseminated in a patient-accessible summary and shared with diabetes support communities to promote equitable awareness of digital health interventions.

Review conflict of interest

Declared individual interests are recorded under team member details.. No additional interests are recorded for this review.

Medical Subject Headings

Adult; Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2; Digital Health; Humans; Quality of Life; Self Efficacy; Self-Management; Socioeconomic Factors; Telemedicine; Text Messaging

PROSPERO version history

No preview available

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